

STRENGTHENING CLINICAL TRIAL REGULATORY AND ETHICAL REVIEW OVERSIGHT IN EAST AFRICA

Deliverable title: D3.3 Development and roll out of the guideline framework to Ethiopia partners

Project acronym: ACCESSAFRICA 2

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe under GA No 101103296.
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Deliverable factsheet:

Project Number:	101103296
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Reviewer(s):	Dr. Bernard Kikaire, David Walusimbi
Approved by	Prof. Rosemarie Bernabe
ABSTRACT:	
Keyword List:	Research, pandemic, Joint Scientific and Ethical Review

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MINUTES FOR THE MEETING HELD WITH JIMMA UNIVERSITY AND UGANDA NATIONAL COUNCIL FOR SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY ON 18TH SEPTEMBER 2024.

In attendance

- i) Dr. Ddamulira Christopher UNCST -*Chairperson*
- ii) Ms. Beth Mutumba UNCST -*Secretary*
- iii) Prof. Gudina Terefe Tucho Jimma University

Absent with Apologies

- i) Ms. Hellen Opolot UNCST

1.0 Communication from UNCST

Dr. Ddamulira welcomed Prof. Gudina to the meeting. Dr. Ddamulira Christopher called the meeting to order at 4:35 pm with an opening prayer. He began by asking the team about the issues with power outages and slow internet speeds that had been plaguing the team's ability in Ethiopia to attend the meeting without interruption.

He informed the members that he hoped that the Joint Scientific and Ethical Review guidelines in Uganda could be adapted in Ethiopia to improve regulatory oversight and efficiency of the regulatory and ethical review processes. Also, the guidelines will improve the turnaround time of the protocols from submission to decision, within the research community for clinical trials in Ethiopia

Matters arising

- a) Prof. Gudina expressed his gratitude to the UNCST for providing time and resources to share the experience in the development of the joint review guidelines. He acknowledged the newness of the joint review guideline in Ethiopia and expressed interest in discussing it further with the relevant stakeholders in Ethiopia.
- b) He informed members about his discussions with regulatory agencies and ethics committees in Ethiopia regarding the adaptation of the joint review guidelines. He noted that he had met with the FDA, Ministry of Education, and National Ethics Review Committee, who expressed interest and promised to support the adaptation process.
- c) He noted the differences between Ethiopia's regulatory review system and Uganda's, noting Ethiopia had only one national ethics committee that sequentially reviews proposals after institutional review boards. He believed that the stakeholder meetings that will be attended by the UNCST team would provide further insights, but the initial response had been positive from the discussions he held prior to the meeting being held.
- d) Prof. Gudina further asked about the conflict-of-interest issues related to sponsors and principal investigators being part of the joint review meeting, but clarification was given by Dr. Ddamulira.

2.0 Presentation on the development process of the joint review guidelines

Dr. Ddamulira discussed the development of joint review guidelines for multi-country studies, which started before the COVID-19 pandemic in 2018. He mentioned that the guidelines were adapted from the WHO-African Vaccine Regulatory Forum (AVAREF), which co-opts different expertise from national committees and regulators together to review multi-country studies.

He highlighted that the Uganda joint review process improved timelines for approval of protocols and the enhanced competence and capacity building for the regulators and ethics committees. He highlighted the importance of various committees, including national regulatory agencies, research committees, institutional animal care and use committees, and subject matter experts.

He noted the role of stakeholders in the review process such as the principal investigator, sponsors, research committees, national regulatory agencies, and subject matter experts as highlighted below:

- a) The convener: According to the guidelines, the Uganda National Council of Science and Technology, manages the process, including distributing research applications, responding to review requests, and compiling comments from stakeholders. The review process typically takes one to three weeks, with emergency trials given one week. The convener also coordinates post-approval processes and manages affiliated agencies such as the Uganda National Research Organization, Uganda National Council for Science and Technology, and Uganda National Drug Authority.
- b) the Institutional Research Ethics Committees, the National Drug Authority (NDA), and the UNCST conduct pre-screening of submitted documents, nominate experts, and raise comments.
- c) The review is held, and comments are shared with the researchers. The Institutional Research Ethics Committees ensure researchers receive approval before submitting to UNCST or NDA for final clearance.

He highlighted the schema that outlines the process from submission to final approval (Please see annex1-presentation). He noted that most protocols submitted for joint review meet the criteria and are not rejected.

3.0 Discussions and Way Forward

Dr. Ddamulira agreed to send the original guidelines from the WHO-African Vaccine Regulatory Forum (AVAREF) and his presentation to Prof. Gudina via email.

The Ethiopian team to read the milestone and deliverable reports on the joint review guidelines development in teams and the EDCTP portal for a better understanding of the process. Members agreed to the need to track the process and achieve the deadline for the role out of the guidelines by 30th June 2025.

Prof. Gudina to organize a stakeholder meeting in Ethiopia to discuss the joint review guidelines development process, identify the roles, and responsibilities of different stakeholders, and potential challenges that may affect the activities for the guideline's development and adaptation in Ethiopia.

The UNCST agreed to have another meeting with the Ethiopian team after the wider stakeholders' consultation to agree on the final road map for the process of development and adaptation of the guidelines in Ethiopia.

Prof. Gudina to identify the lead agency for the joint review guidelines development in Ethiopian during the stakeholder consultation meetings.

Signature

Secretary: Date:

Chairperson: Date:

Annex 1: Presentation slides.

ACCESS AFRICA 2

Adaptation of the Joint Scientific and Ethical Review of Research in Ethiopia

Dr. Christopher Ddamulira
Co-Investigator, Uganda National Council for Science and Technology (UNCST)

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- General Provisions of the Guidelines
- Role of National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs)
- Roles & Responsibilities of Joint Review Participants
- The Joint Review Process
- Other important aspects

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General Provisions of the Guidelines

- The Joint Scientific and Ethical Review Guidelines set forth a **framework** for which National Regulatory Agencies (NRAs), Research Ethics Committees (RECs), Institutional Animal Care and Use Committees (IACUCs), subject matter experts, and appropriate stakeholders in a given field shall consider while conducting such reviews.
- The guidelines have been adapted from the framework of the African Vaccine Regulatory Forum (**AVAREF**) of the World Health Organisation (WHO).

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Joint Scientific and Ethical Review Guidelines is intended to:

- Enhance **Quality of reviews**
- **Optimize timelines** for review and approval
- **Exchange and validate findings** between NRAs ,Research Ethics Committees (RECs),IACUCs, IBCs and Experts
- **Capacity strengthening platform**

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Roles & Responsibilities of Joint Review Participants

IACUC=Institutional Animal Care & Use Committee
NRA=National Regulatory Agency
REC=Research Ethics Committee
SME=Subject Matter Expert

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Convener (UNCST Secretariat)

- Managing stakeholder representation for the Joint review meetings
- Distributing research applications to reviewers
- Responding to reviewer requests and providing information exchange
- Appointing a Chairperson
- Compiling comments for the Joint review process
- Coordinating post-approval processes.

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National Regulatory Agencies

- Pre-screening submitted documents
- Nominating representatives for the Joint review meetings
- Reviewing the research application package, and raising comments
- Issuing regulatory decisions
- Conducting ongoing review of the study, and undertaking other relevant tasks related to the Joint review process

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Institutional Committees (ICs)

- Recommending protocol submission to UNCST for Joint review consideration
- Pre-screening documents
- Ensuring quorum of the IC
- Reviewing research application packages
- Obtaining study approval
- Conducting reviews, and participating in joint monitoring

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Institutional Committees (ICs)

- Ensure PIs receive approval and proceed to the UNCST for registration and the NDA (where applicable) to obtain a certificate for the conduct of the clinical trial

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Invited reviewers and Interested Parties

- Subject matter experts and Interested Parties shall be identified by the UNCST in collaboration with other NRAs
- Provide subject expert opinion and raise queries on the submission

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PI and Sponsors

- The PI and sponsors must submit the necessary study documents
- Attend the Joint review meeting
- Present an overview of the study, and respond to comments
- Addressing the comments generated in the joint review meeting

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Schema

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Other aspects for consideration

Joint Monitoring & Inspection

All protocols approved through a joint review process shall be monitored through a joint inspection by UNCST, UNHRO, NDA, and REC.

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Conclusion

- The guidelines are intended to streamline and ensure the smooth completion of the Joint review process, requiring all participants to comply with the specific provisions in these guidelines.

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